

BPEmb-XLMR Based Hybrid Model For Text Summarizer In English Language

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Abstract— Automatic text summarization is a very good application in the increasing amount of online news. But the work of summarizing transliterated and code-mixed news is a big problem one, for the ongoing methods because any news in these formats does not have standard unit of language and also has noisy patterns. Existing extractive methods such as TF-IDF and Text Rank are not able to find relation between words and the ongoing seq2seq models with recursive neural networks face issues with long-distance relation between words and handling transliterated unit of language not present in the same vocabulary. This paper proposes improvements to a Hybrid Model for transliterated news articles, which consists of a custom-designed Neural Embedding Model, FastText abstractive method for the unsupervised extractive process, and a XLMR for finding relation. To improve the model, we suggest a more improved implementation of the Hybrid Model with a combined subword and multilingual embedding technique, graph-based neural network abstractive summarization, and a transformer-based abstractive method utilizing the pointer-generator network.

INTRODUCTION

The digital media is increasing at very fast pace and a large volume of text is uploaded on a daily basis in news outlets, social media, blogs, and online forums. This increases the need of automatic text summarization to enable individuals to see the information faster and view it in a broader sense. Summarization will reduce lengthy documents to brief summary that has the original meaning and important information.

In other multi-language countries, most of the news summaries are written in the regional languages such as Hindi or Telugu using the English alphabet. Such a text makes the process of summarization difficult due to the non-uniformity of spelling, use of different words, and at the same time also having us of English words. The existing NLP approaches are unable to handle these noisy and non-standard text, therefore resulting poor or faulty summaries.

Older summarization processes that select sentences at random in a document, such as TF-IDF and Text rank summarising cannot generate new text. They are quick but does not give meaningful comprehension and give repetitive/confusing summaries. The new models, employing neural networks aims to produce new summaries, attempt to produce human-associated text, but struggle with lengthy documents, unknown transliterated words and maintaining the meaning same as the original text.

Text Summarization, is very important part of natural language processing, aims to reduce text while still having its original meaning. This process is achieved through extractive and abstractive methods.[7]

The recent developments in the area of deep learning has improved the performance of text summarization, but the problems faced during the design of an effective summarization

system of the data dominated by transliteration draw a number a number of research challenges:

Semantic context loss in long documents with traditional repetitive models, vocabulary lackness and difference in spelling due to transliteration text, repeated and partiality in extractive news which are important in today's news applications.

So, understanding the given problems which are present in the text summarization we can get a better understanding on the issue and work on it in the positive direction.

Below are the given problems in the text summary field today which are major problems:

1. **Identifying the content and giving priority** is a Major challenge today in large volume text
2. **Reducing hallucinations** in the trained network is a difficult task with proper use of training and testing dataset.
3. **Handling Long Documents** is also another big problem.
4. Creating a proper structured embedding problem which can handle translated word issue and can be used as multi-lingual model.
5. **Handling non-Text data** is also a major issue because in many given paragraphs other content like audio, image, video are also included for which the there is no embedding done causing issue in summary creation.

This paper will suggest a hybrid use of text summarization which will give better summary and also work with transliterated news articles to handle the words meaning problem and giving a better embedding of the words. The approach will join the task-related word representations, extractive sentence selection, and neural abstractive generation in order to get structural, meaning and semantic value. Reducing errors in feature representations and attention-based finding systems are used to increase the literature flow and get important transliterated words. Testing of good news dataset has proven the provided method to produce more better and informative summaries, as opposed to traditional extractive and earlier used neural models.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 contains a review of related work in texts

summarization and texts processing technique used in used in earlier work. Section III will give the proposed methodology and model architecture. Section IV will show the result on the trained dataset. Section and the paper ends in section VI the future research directions. Finally, there came the citation and references of the research done by the considered people.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There are several methods of summarizing text, which provide us with an in-depth overview of the text and deal with words belonging to other languages. The research paper makes us understand on what we learn next and how we can improve on hybrid summary generation.

The paper [1] applies a hybrid text summarization method, which is capable of processing mixed-language text and provides a superior summary. A custom Neural Word Embedding (NEM) is constructed at the start, therefore, regional words can be comprehended more effectively in the given language. Subsequently every sentence is converted into a vector. TextRank identifies the most important items of the content to be summarized when a similarity graph is generated. A combination Seq2Seq model then generates a natural and human-like summary. The model is built with:

- Encoder: 3 layer Bi-directional
- Decoder: LSTM with Attention
- Beam search for better word generation

The paper [2] was read to get to know the working of the Artificial neural networks both in supervised and unsupervised modes. It outlines the process through which the network learns, through the adjustment of the weights depending on the data it is getting.

The [3] research conducted a study on the TextRank with the currently available extractive summarization systems like the TF-IDF and the TextRank. These techniques pick the sentences off the original text but it does not create text. Their reading is speedy and they might lose the meaning, therefore its summary can be misdirected or incorrect. Abstractive models are attempting to produce more human sounding summaries, but they fail with large documents, out of vocabulary words and maintaining the same meaning between the document and the summary.

Deep learning has now made summarization better, although it does not work with transliterated and mixed-language texts. Among the problems, there are the wrong meaning of transliteration, out of vocabulary words, spelling variations, inability to retrieve the meaning of very huge texts, and the absence of correct and useful news summaries to be used in the actual world.

The FastText model to classify the Kurdish texts is presented and evaluated in this research paper [4]. Kurdish is an arduous language with relatively scanty information to be trained thus difficult to classify. FastText was tested against 8 other machine-learning models (SVM, Naive Bayes, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, KNN, Decision Tree, SGD and BERT). FastText showed high performance in terms of accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score compared to the others using four Kurdish datasets

(KNDH, MKD, KMD -77000, FuefdiSent). It also trained and was utilized faster. FastText is not a root meaning ignoring word embedding such as other popular word embeddings; it makes use of continuous n-gram models. The study of FastText helps us to comprehend the decision making and make better models of text classification in the future.

Old vs New Model Comparison (Vertical)

Figure 1. Flow Diagram Old Model Vs New Model

This diagram show the structure flow of the old Technique in Previous model in comparison to the new model representing difference between them related to how they will work.

Unlike many word embeddings, fastText does not ignore the morphology of words. This method is based on a continuous n skip-grams [8].

The deep investigation into fastText helps us understand the decision making process as well as provides heuristic ideas on how to design more effective text classification models in the future.[9]

In this research paper[5] the procedures of the construction of the graph data in Graph Convolutional Networks (GCN) and Graph Attention Networks (GAT) are discussed, as well as how to add more layers and use the data on more neighbour nodes. Research indicates that when model is trained with a very small dataset, the model underfits; when over-trained, it over-smooths representation of nodes so that all nodes appear alike. The authors propose as a solution mathematically estimating the graph to make the difference in hyperparameters smaller and allowing

computers to work at high performance. It is demonstrated in the analysis that both practical and theoretical advantages of creating superior GCN and GAT methods in grouping of nodes exist.

According to this, a graph is drawn, in which the representation of vectors establishes the relationship not only among the neighbouring nodes but also between the remote nodes. The interactions and routing of each node to the others are computed to come up with a final representation.

PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Text summarization enables to create a summary of the given content. The summary of the given content should be correct and to the point. But right now many models which create summary suffer from hallucination and creating summary which is not correct or has in it the repeated content.

To address this issue we are creating a hybrid model that will create a natural embedding first and also using can generate its own word if required from the given which suits best for the summary. Here we are also using mutli-language text that will handle the transliterated words also and along with also create summary of the articles that contains noisy or different language words.

A. Data Collection

First the data will be collected either from the news article or other and then based on further process can continue. We can use the text that can be of the following types;

- Monolingual text
- Multilingual text

B. Data Preprocessing

After the data is collected it will be processed and cleaned. Following steps will be followed to clean the collected text which will be further used:

1. **Text Cleaning** will involve removing tags, line-breaks, commas and also white-spaces if present.
2. **Sentence Segmentation** in this words will be broken down into small-small parts.
3. **Tokenization** in this the words are changes into there root grammar form which will be help in the better vector representation of the words when it will be needed to fiind the relation between the words and based on which it will be used to determine which word to use and which word not to use.

C. Hybrid Embedding Generation

In this the words will be changes into there vector representation which will help to gather meaning of words easily.

1. Fast Text Embeddings

Fast Text is the representation of the characters in the n gram,

It is helpful for representing the different language words and can handle the noisy words also easily.

$$E_{FT}(w) = \sum_{g \in G(w)} v_g$$

where is the set of n-grams of characters for the word.

2. XLM-R Contextual Embeddings

It will be used to find the relation between the words and determine the relation between them over long distances.

$$E_{XLM}(s_i) = \text{Transformer}(s_i)$$

where is a word contained in the training dataset

3. BPEmb (Byte-Pair Embeddings)

It will break words into smaller words embedding and help to understand words even if they were not present. It does it by breaking the words and then merge the vector to understand the meaning of the words.

$$E_{BP}(s_i) = \sum_{k=1}^m e_k$$

4. Hybrid Embedding Fusion

In this embedding there will be combination of the earlier to embedding resulting in creating hybrid embedding which will be able to grasp meaning of almost all the words.

$$E(s_i) = [E_{FT}(s_i) \oplus E_{XLM}(s_i) \oplus E_{BP}(s_i)]$$

This hybrid representation improves coverage able to handle various types of words in comparison to simple single

Embedding which were used earlier.

D. Graph-Based Extractive Summarization

In the given text we will select the most important sentences from it rather than including the ones which have less representation and does contain the core meaning of the text that has to be summarized.

1. Graph Construction

- A sentence becomes a node.

$$G = (V, E)$$

- where:

$$V = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$$

- To find which words to use we will use cosine similarity to find the relation between the words and base of this determine which words should be used and which one should not be used.

$$w_{ij} = \frac{E(s_i) \cdot E(s_j)}{\|E(s_i)\| \|E(s_j)\|}$$

2. Graph Neural Network (GCN / GAT)

We use Graph Convolutional Network or Graph Attention Network to identify the importance of

every sentence and then from it select the ones which are most important.

$$H^{(l+1)} = \sigma(\tilde{D}^{-1/2} \tilde{A} \tilde{D}^{-1/2} H^{(l)} W^{(l)})$$

here:

1. \tilde{A} is the adjacency matrix
2. $H^{(l)}$ is the node representation at layer l

3. Sentence Ranking

The sentences receive weight indicating their importance. The final summary contains sentence that have highest weight.

E. Abstractive Summarization Module

At last we are using transformer Encoder-Decoder which will the final fluent summary of the given text presented to it.

1. Transformer Encoder-Decoder

The encoder will receive the token from here the semantic relationship will be create and attentive semantic words created which will help to determine the relationship between the words

Whether it is long-distance dependency or the short-range dependency between the words.

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V$$

At last the decoder creates the summary it uses one word at time and create a summary using previous used word and at the same time also finding out the next word which should be used. Where the pointer-generator will determine whether to use that word or create another word.

Transformer decoder allows parallel computing making it easier to handle very lengthy and long text and create a summary at very fast pace making it easy to produce the summary.

Transformer architectures, including BERT, GPT and T5, have transformed the miss-understandings about summarization to long-range dependencies comprising attention mechanisms to produce logical coherent and context-specific summaries[6].

2. Pointer-Generator Mechanism

At each step it checks the probability of the words based on which it determines whether to use the words from the existing summary or create a new word meaning for the summary.

$$P(w) = p_{gen}P_{vocab}(w) + (1 - p_{gen})P_{copy}(w)$$

This allows the model to either **generate** new words or **copy** words directly from the source text.

This can easily solve the problems like OOV

(out-of-vocabulary),

Rare words or transliterated words easily and as result

there is very less possibility of error and helps to create a smooth and effective summary.

Detailed Component Diagram (Vertical)

Figure 2. Flow Diagram of the Proposed Model

This is the flow diagram of the proposed theory showcasing the model usage and the structural flow relating how the execution of the model will take place and also the effective modelling used to create the summary and provide the required result as needed.

CONCLUSION

This Study explored the different summarising hybrid model that can be used to create a effective summary using **FastText** , **BPEMB** and **Graph /GCNAT**.

At last we were able to create summary which can handle the Transliterated words and also reduce the noise by creating an effective embedding and produce final result which are more concise and as humanly as possible.

FUTURE WORK

Future studies can focus on improving the training methodology involving **Cross-Entropy Loss**, **Model Evaluation and Interpretability** which can help in creating even better summary and can be the new scope of research and work that we look into forward for the future reference.

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